

THE EFFECT OF JOB SATISFACTION ON WORK DISCIPLINE THROUGH SOCIAL SUPPORT AS AN INTERVENING VARIABLE AT PT FAMILY AURORA NUSANTARA FOOD AND BEVERAGES COMPANY

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Received : 01 January 2026

Accepted : 10 February 2026

Revised : 17 January 2026

Published : 28 February 2026

Abstract

This study aims to analyze the effect of Job Satisfaction on Work Discipline among employees, with Social Support as an intervening variable at PT Family Aurora Nusantara. The study employs a quantitative approach with 89 employees as respondents, selected through purposive sampling. Data were collected using a Likert-scale questionnaire. Data analysis was conducted using the Partial Least Squares–Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) method with the assistance of SmartPLS 4.0. The results indicate that both Job Satisfaction and Social Support have a positive and significant effect on Work Discipline. In addition, Job Satisfaction also has a positive and significant effect on Social Support. The test of indirect effects shows that Social Support is able to mediate the effect of Job Satisfaction on employees' Work Discipline. These findings suggest that improving the quality of work life and job satisfaction can strengthen social support in the workplace, which ultimately enhances employees' work discipline.

Keywords: *Job Satisfaction, Work Discipline, Social Support, Food and Beverages Company*

INTRODUCTION

The food and beverages (FnB) industry in Indonesia is a rapidly growing sector that contributes significantly to the national economy. Conceptually, the FnB industry encompasses restaurants, cafés, food stalls, and food and beverage producers. Shifts in consumer behavior have transformed dining activities from merely fulfilling basic needs into social and emotional experiences that are both aesthetic and trendy. This demands professional and consistent service, making business success dependent not only on product quality but also on service quality, with employee performance and discipline being crucial factors in maintaining customer satisfaction (Bizhare, 2024). The FnB industry heavily relies on human resource quality, as operations are determined by employees' competencies, service, and discipline in adhering to standard operating procedures (SOPs) and work responsibilities (Sartika et al., 2021). However, work pressure and irregular operating hours often trigger tardiness and turnover (Arifin & Putra, 2022). Data indicate that approximately 30% of FnB employees still violate rules, and 65% experience work-related stress, affecting motivation and discipline (Ministry of Manpower of the Republic of Indonesia, 2022). Work discipline is defined as the awareness of complying with rules, influenced by factors such as leadership, compensation, fairness, and harmonious work relationships; it is therefore closely linked to psychological and organizational aspects rather than being an isolated trait (Prawoto, 2023).

Several studies demonstrate a relationship between job satisfaction and work discipline. Wayan (2023) reported a significant positive coefficient between job satisfaction and work discipline. Similar results were found by Yanti and Trianasari (2022), with a contribution of 70.2% at Hotel Brits Resort Lovina. Silalahi (2020) also stated that job satisfaction strongly affects discipline. Factors such as fair compensation, work environment, leadership, and the nature of the job also influence job satisfaction (Yeyen & Nabila, 2022). Thus, higher job satisfaction increases the likelihood of employees being disciplined. In addition to job satisfaction, social support plays an important role in shaping discipline. Verlita et al. (2023) found a significant positive relationship between discipline and social support among employees at PT Prima Soeka Buana Bekasi. Parker (2023) explained that social support functions as a buffer against work-related stress. Akbar (2022) and Kumala (2023) noted that support from supervisors and colleagues enhances employees' sense of security and discipline. Sukamto et al. (2022) emphasized that emotional and instrumental support encourages rule compliance, while Hendari (2021) found a significant contribution of social support to performance. These findings suggest that social support has the potential to act as

an intervening variable between job satisfaction and work discipline.

Other studies further support this relationship. Eriawati et al. (2023) reported a correlation of 0.588 between social support and work productivity among BNN Samarinda employees. Rahama (2021) documented a positive correlation with psychological well-being ($r = 0.433$). Tumaruddin et al. (2021) confirmed that social support enhances commitment and work well-being, while Rofi & Purwanda (2022) stated that it strengthens psychological stability under high work pressure. Theoretically, social support can strengthen the relationship between job satisfaction and discipline. Fluctuations in discipline have also been observed at PT Family Aurora Nusantara, a food and beverages company in Probolinggo Regency. HRD data from 2022–2025 indicate that the lowest attendance and highest tardiness occurred in 2024, despite the company implementing split-shift systems and salary deduction policies. Work discipline is essential for maintaining consistent service quality in the FnB industry (Huang & Sofiani, 2022). Interviews with 11 employees revealed that although some were satisfied with the work environment and received good social support, this did not fully align with actual discipline levels, as tardiness was still observed due to fatigue and operational workload. These findings indicate a gap between theoretical expectations that job satisfaction and social support enhance discipline and empirical conditions in the field. Based on this phenomenon, a research gap exists between theory and practice. Theoretically, job satisfaction and social support should enhance discipline (Robbins & Judge, 2017), yet field data show inconsistent results. The novelty of this study lies in testing social support as an intervening variable in the relationship between job satisfaction and work discipline in the FnB industry operating under a split-shift system. This study aims to analyze the effect of job satisfaction on work discipline through social support at PT Family Aurora Nusantara. Theoretically, it contributes to organizational behavior research. Practically, the findings are expected to provide a foundation for management strategies that emphasize employee well-being and social support to enhance work discipline.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Work Discipline

Work discipline refers to employees' behavior that demonstrates compliance with organizational rules and responsibilities (Asrianto, 2025). From a work psychology perspective, discipline is influenced not only by control or sanctions but also by personal awareness and commitment (Winata, 2025). Robbins & Judge (2019) explain that discipline is shaped through the interaction of motivation, perceptions of fairness, and support from the work environment. Mangkunegara (2011) adds that leadership, compensation, and supervisory systems also affect the level of discipline. Various studies, including Pratowo (2023), indicate that discipline plays a crucial role in maintaining productivity and work quality. However, most research still emphasizes formal rules over psychological and social factors. In fact, disciplinary behavior is also influenced by emotional conditions and workplace relationships. Therefore, it is important to study work discipline more comprehensively by considering affective and social factors.

Job Satisfaction

Job satisfaction is an individual's evaluation of their work, reflecting the alignment between expectations and reality (Wayan, 2023). This satisfaction encompasses positive feelings regarding compensation, work environment, relationships with supervisors, and development opportunities (Putri & Rafiqah, 2024; Tiong, 2023). Employees who feel satisfied usually exhibit stronger organizational commitment. Several studies indicate that job satisfaction is positively associated with work discipline (Wayan, 2023). This implies that the higher the job satisfaction, the higher the adherence to work rules. However, many studies still consider satisfaction as a direct factor without explaining the processes in between. In fact, this relationship can be influenced by social factors within the organization. This highlights the need for a model that can explain this relationship more clearly and in an integrated manner.

Social Support

Social support refers to emotional, informational, and tangible assistance received by individuals in the workplace (Taylor, 2022). This support can come from supervisors as well as coworkers. The presence of social support helps improve psychological well-being and reduce work-related stress (Muliiany, 2024). Gardner (in Akbar, 2022) states that attention and recognition from the work environment can strengthen employees' sense of belonging to the organization. Putriana & Nulipata (2023) and Ramadhana & Ibrahim (2023) also show that social support affects job satisfaction and work discipline. Nevertheless, the role of social support in research models varies; some studies treat it as a direct factor, while others position it as a mediator. This variation indicates that the role of social

support still requires further testing. Therefore, this study places social support as an intervening variable between job satisfaction and work discipline.

METHOD

This study is a quantitative research employing an explanatory research approach, aimed at examining the effect of job satisfaction (X) on employees' work discipline (Y) with social support (Z) as an intervening variable. The population of this study consisted of all permanent employees in the food and beverages department at PT Family Aurora Nusantara, totaling 89 individuals. Referring to Arikunto (2018) in Huang & Sofiani (2023), if the population is fewer than 100, the entire population is used as the sample. Therefore, this study employed a total sampling technique with 89 respondents from various divisions. Data were collected using a questionnaire with a five-point Likert scale. The work discipline instrument consisted of 24 items covering rule compliance, time management, attendance, commitment, behavioral consistency, and responsibility. The social support scale comprised 16 items, including emotional, instrumental, informational, and evaluative support, while the job satisfaction scale included 16 items covering salary, work environment, interpersonal relationships, and job characteristics. Data analysis was conducted quantitatively using SmartPLS through testing the outer model (convergent validity, discriminant validity, and composite reliability), the inner model, and hypothesis testing.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Respondent Characteristics

Based on the analysis of data from 89 respondents, 42 were male (52.63%) and 47 were female (47.37%), indicating a relatively balanced gender composition. The majority of respondents were aged 21–30 years, totaling 62 individuals (80.70%), followed by 31–40 years with 17 respondents (10.53%), and over 41 years with 10 respondents (8.77%), demonstrating a dominance of the productive age group. Regarding education, most respondents were high school graduates, totaling 61 individuals, while 28 respondents held a bachelor's degree. In terms of work experience, the majority had 2–3 years of experience (51 respondents), followed by 1 year (20 respondents), and 5–7 years (17 respondents). Overall, the respondents were dominated by productive-age employees with secondary education and relatively short to medium work tenure.

Measurement Model Evaluation (Outer Model Testing)

The measurement model was evaluated to ensure that all indicators are valid and reliable in reflecting the study's latent constructs. The evaluation included convergent validity, discriminant validity, and construct reliability. The first test was convergent validity. Convergent validity was assessed using outer loading values and the Average Variance Extracted (AVE), with criteria of outer loading ≥ 0.70 and AVE ≥ 0.50 . After eliminating indicators that did not meet the criteria, all remaining indicators were declared valid.

Table 1. Summary of Outer Loadings

Variable	Loading Range
Work Discipline (Y)	0.770 – 0.916
Social Support (Z)	0.799 – 0.896
Job Satisfaction (X)	0.861 – 0.924

Table 1 shows that all indicators for each construct have values above 0.70, thereby meeting the convergent validity criteria. Next, the AVE was tested as follows:

Table 2. Average Variance Extracted (AVE)

Latent Variable	AVE
Work Discipline (Y)	0.740
Social Support (Z)	0.703
Job Satisfaction (X)	0.799

Table 2 shows that all constructs have AVE values above 0.50, indicating that each construct explains more than 50% of the variance in its indicators. Thus, all variables meet the convergent validity criteria. The next step was discriminant validity testing. Discriminant validity was evaluated using cross-loading values. The criterion is that the loading of an indicator on its own construct must be higher than its loading on other constructs. The summary of

cross-loading calculations is presented in the table below:

Table 3. Summary of Cross Loadings

Construct	Loading on Own Construct	Loading on Other Constructs
Work Discipline (Y)	0.770 – 0.916	0.496 – 0.757
Social Support (Z)	0.799 – 0.896	0.502 – 0.741
Job Satisfaction (X)	0.861 – 0.924	0.520 – 0.666

The results in Table 3 indicate that all indicators of Work Discipline, Social Support, and Job Satisfaction have the highest loadings on their respective constructs compared to other constructs. Therefore, the model meets the discriminant validity criteria based on the cross-loading approach, demonstrating that each construct in this study can be empirically distinguished.

In addition to cross-loading, discriminant validity was also tested using the Heterotrait–Monotrait Ratio (HTMT) method. The results are as follows:

Table 4. Heterotrait–Monotrait Ratio (HTMT)

Construct	Work Discipline	Social Support	Job Satisfaction
Work Discipline (Y)	-	0.810	0.720
Social Support (Z)	0.810	-	0.689
Job Satisfaction (X)	0.720	0.689	-

Table 4 shows that the HTMT values for all variable pairs are below 0.90, in accordance with Hair et al. (2022), indicating that discriminant validity has been achieved. Next, construct reliability was tested. Construct reliability was assessed using Cronbach’s Alpha, rho_A, and Composite Reliability, with the criteria ≥ 0.70 .

Table 5. Construct Reliability

Variable	Cronbach’s Alpha	rho_A	Composite Reliability	Description
Job Satisfaction (X)	0.967	0.968	0.971	Reliable
Work Discipline (Y)	0.983	0.984	0.985	Reliable
Social Support (Z)	0.986	0.987	0.987	Reliable

Table 5 shows that all variables have reliability values above 0.70. Therefore, the constructs of Job Satisfaction, Work Discipline, and Social Support are declared reliable and suitable for testing the structural model (inner model).

Structural Model Evaluation (Inner Model)

The structural model (inner model) was evaluated to analyze the relationships among latent variables and the model’s ability to explain the endogenous variables. The tests included the coefficient of determination (R^2), predictive relevance (Q^2), and effect size (f^2) using SmartPLS 4.0. The first test was the R^2 coefficient:

Table 6. R-Square Values

Variable	R^2	Adjusted R^2
Work Discipline (Y)	0.710	0.700
Social Support (Z)	0.637	0.629

Based on Table 6, the R^2 test results show the extent to which exogenous variables explain the endogenous variables. The Work Discipline (Y) variable has an R^2 value of 0.710, indicating that 71.0% of the variation in Work Discipline can be explained by Job Satisfaction and Social Support, while the remaining 29.0% is influenced by factors outside the model. This value falls into the strong category. Meanwhile, Social Support (Z) has an R^2 value of 0.637, meaning 63.7% of its variation can be explained by Job Satisfaction, with 36.3% influenced by other variables outside the study. Overall, these values indicate that the model has good and substantial explanatory power. Next, the Q^2 test was conducted:

Table 7. Q-Square Values

Variable	Q ²
Work Discipline (Y)	0.506
Social Support (Z)	0.425
Job Satisfaction (X)	0.000

Table 7 shows that Q² values were obtained through the blindfolding procedure to assess the model's predictive ability. The results indicate that the Q² values for Work Discipline and Social Support are 0.506 and 0.425, respectively, both greater than 0. This suggests that the model has good predictive capability for the endogenous variables. Q² values above 0.35 indicate strong predictive relevance. The Q² value for Job Satisfaction is 0.000 because it is an exogenous variable, and thus it is not predicted by other variables in the model. Next, the F-Square (f²) test was conducted:

Table 8. F-Square Values (f²)

Variable	Work Discipline (Y)	Social Support (Z)	Job Satisfaction (X2)
Work Discipline (Y)	-	-	-
Social Support (Z)	0.227	-	-
Job Satisfaction (X2)	0.145	0.240	-

Table 8 shows that the F-Square results indicate the magnitude of the effect of each independent variable on the dependent variable in the research model. In general, the larger the F-Square value, the greater the influence of the variable in explaining the variance of the dependent variable.

Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis testing was conducted using the bootstrapping procedure in SmartPLS 4.0 at a 5% significance level ($\alpha = 0.05$). The testing criteria state that a hypothesis is accepted if the p-value < 0.05, and rejected if the p-value > 0.05. Based on the path coefficient analysis, the hypothesis testing results are as follows:

Figure 1. Path Model with t-Values and p-Values

Based on Figure 1, it can be observed that a hypothesis is accepted if the p-value < 0.05. The results of the data analysis can be seen in the testing of direct effects and indirect effects hypotheses.

Table 9. Direct Effect Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis	Variable Relationship	Path Coefficient	t-Value	p-Value	Result
H1	Social Support → Work Discipline	0.426	3.468	0.001	Accepted
H2	Job Satisfaction → Work Discipline	0.282	2.819	0.005	Accepted
H3	Job Satisfaction → Social Support	0.365	3.442	0.001	Accepted

The direct effect test was conducted to determine the magnitude of direct influence between variables, with the criteria of t -statistic > 1.96 and p -value < 0.05 . Based on Table 9, the analysis shows that Social Support has a positive and significant effect on Work Discipline ($\beta = 0.426$; $p = 0.001$), so H1 is accepted. Job Satisfaction also has a positive and significant effect on Work Discipline ($\beta = 0.282$; $p = 0.005$), so H2 is accepted. In addition, Job Satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on Social Support ($\beta = 0.365$; $p = 0.001$), so H3 is accepted. These findings indicate that improving job satisfaction and social support directly contributes to enhancing employees' work discipline.

Table 10. Indirect Effect Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis	Mediating Relationship	Path Coefficient	t-Value	p-Value	Result
H4	Job Satisfaction → Social Support → Work Discipline	0.155	2.157	0.031	Accepted

The indirect effect test was conducted to determine the role of Social Support as a mediating variable between Job Satisfaction and Work Discipline. Based on Table 10, the bootstrapping results show that Job Satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on Work Discipline through Social Support ($\beta = 0.155$; $t = 2.157$; $p = 0.031 < 0.05$). Therefore, H4 is accepted. These results indicate that Social Support functions as a mediator, where increased Job Satisfaction encourages higher perceived Social Support among employees, which in turn strengthens Work Discipline.

Discussion

The results of the study indicate that the composition of respondents was relatively balanced between males (52.63%) and females (47.37%), with the majority aged 21–30 years, reflecting a productive-age workforce. Most respondents had completed high school, while the remainder held a bachelor's degree, and the majority had 2–3 years of work experience, indicating employees at a developing stage of experience. These characteristics depict a workforce with high energy but still in the process of gaining experience, which can influence perceptions of job satisfaction and social support. The predominance of younger employees also fosters active social interactions, which can strengthen relationships among colleagues. In this context, the discussion of the hypotheses becomes more focused and relevant.

The first hypothesis (H1) testing showed that social support has a positive and significant effect on work discipline. A path coefficient of 0.426 with a p -value of 0.001 indicates a fairly strong relationship. This means that the higher the support from supervisors and coworkers, the greater the employees' work discipline. Social support provides psychological safety and reinforces emotional attachment to the organization, motivating employees to comply with rules and consistently fulfill their work responsibilities. These findings align with Hendari (2021), who stated that social support fosters positive work behaviors. Sukamto et al. (2022) also found that employees who feel valued tend to be more disciplined. Descriptively, indicators of coworker relationships received high ratings from respondents, although a small proportion of employees still showed suboptimal punctuality.

The second hypothesis (H2) confirmed that job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on work discipline. A path coefficient of 0.282 with a p -value of 0.005 demonstrates a meaningful relationship. Employees who are satisfied with their job, work environment, and reward system tend to comply more with organizational rules. Job satisfaction fosters psychological attachment that encourages responsibility in performing tasks. These results are consistent with Yanti and Trianasari (2022), who reported a positive relationship between job satisfaction and work discipline. Silalahi (2020) also emphasized that high job satisfaction increases compliance with operational standards. Nevertheless, relatively low evaluations were still observed in workload and work-life balance aspects, indicating that improvements in job satisfaction need to be comprehensive. Thus, organizations must maintain the quality of the work environment to ensure consistent discipline.

The third hypothesis (H3) showed that job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on social support. A path coefficient of 0.365 with a p -value of 0.001 indicates a strong relationship. Employees who are satisfied tend to be more open in interacting with colleagues and supervisors. Job satisfaction creates a positive emotional climate, making communication more effective. This supports the development of cooperation and solidarity within the workplace. These findings align with Hendrawijaya and Rizal (2022), who explained that job satisfaction enhances the quality of interpersonal relationships. Respondents with high satisfaction levels perceived higher social support. Positive social interactions form the foundation of a supportive work environment. Therefore, job satisfaction plays a strategic role in strengthening organizational social aspects.

The fourth hypothesis (H4) demonstrated that job satisfaction positively and significantly affects work discipline through social support. A path coefficient of 0.155 with a p-value of 0.031 indicates a significant mediating effect. This means that job satisfaction impacts work discipline not only directly but also indirectly by enhancing social support. Satisfied employees tend to build harmonious and mutually supportive working relationships. This support strengthens commitment to following rules and fulfilling responsibilities. These results are consistent with Yanti and Trianasari (2022), who emphasized the importance of social relationships in improving discipline. Hendari (2021) also noted that social support acts as a psychosocial mechanism bridging work behavior. Thus, social support is proven to be a partial mediator in this study, enriching the understanding of relationships among the investigated variables.

Overall, this study shows that job satisfaction and social support jointly contribute to shaping work discipline. Job satisfaction influences individual attitudes and perceptions, while social support reinforces positive behaviors in the organizational environment. The combination of these factors significantly contributes to improving employee discipline. Organizations should pay attention to psychological well-being and the quality of social relationships, while implementing formal rules in a humanistic and supportive manner. A positive work environment encourages employees to be more orderly and responsible, enabling sustainable improvement in work discipline.

CONCLUSION

Based on the analysis using Partial Least Squares (PLS), it can be concluded that social support and job satisfaction have positive and significant effects on employees' work discipline. Social support enhances psychological safety and emotional attachment, thereby promoting adherence to work rules. Job satisfaction also positively influences discipline, both directly and indirectly through social support as a mediating variable. In other words, employees who feel satisfied tend to build better social relationships, which in turn strengthens disciplined behavior. Overall, psychological and social factors play an essential role in shaping employee discipline.

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